

A Comprehensive Review on Biomedical Application of Plant-derived Essential Oils

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Antimicrobial activities
Essential oils Medicinal
plants Pathogenic
microbes

ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants have been used for the treatment of various ailments from the earliest time. The medicinal values of plants are due to the presence of an organic substance known as “Essential oils”. Essential oils are volatile, organic plant-based substances that are extracted from the various parts of aromatic plants. They are produced as secondary metabolites of the plants. Essential oils are well-known and well-documented world widely because of their therapeutic potential applications. The biomedical applications of essential oils are due to their bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, flavonoids, alcohols, terpenoids, and hydrocarbons. These bioactive compounds make essential oils more precise in their mechanism of action against pathogenic bacteria, viruses, and fungi. Essential oils and their bioactive compounds inhibit the growth of spoilage and infectious microorganism. Essential oils are very effective scavengers of free radicals. Essential oils can be used as anti-cancer and anti-diabetic agents. Hence, essential oils could be used as better supplements against pathogenic microbes because of their antiseptic potential. This review summarized the antimicrobial, antioxidant, antidiabetic, and anti-cancer applications potential of natural plants product and their mechanism of action for the inhibition of pathogenic microbes.

Introduction

Based on their promising actions against numerous disease-causing pathogens, the majority of plants that found use in ethnic medicine have been reported [1]. Research is moving quickly toward a better functional knowledge of medicinal plants, which has given rise to a model for around 25–50% of the medications currently on the market [2]. Useful plants have a variety of antimicrobial properties; the majority work together to reduce the negative effects of synthetic medications [3] While others operate as quorum quenchers.

Although artificial compounds are more important for the prevention and therapies of several diseases but natural compounds also have been exploited because of their unique medicinal properties [4]. The usage of

artificial drugs against numerous pathogenic disorders is restricted because of their high toxicity, carcinogenic level, and hazardous impact on the environment [5]. Recently, the detrimental influences of synthetic drugs have directed to search the novel alternatives from natural products [6]. Due to intensive its medicinal potential, natural compounds gained more interest worldwide [7]. An extensive diversity of valued constituents can be attained from plants [8]. Plants-derived products such as essential oils are the best example of natural compounds and gained more attention because of their suitable chemical profiling and biological potential [9]. Essential oils are well-documented for their therapeutic potential against various pathogenic diseases. Hence, the use of essential

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oils is promising approach to combat devastating maladies [10].

Essential oils

Essential oils are volatile complex organic substances that originated from plants. They are the aromatic secondary metabolites of plants. The term essential oils were coined by Paracelsus von Hohenheim (Swiss reformer of medicine) in the 16th century. EOs are a polar and nonpolar mixture of natural compounds [11]. EOs used for thousands of years and possess multiple functions such as playing a defensive role against microorganism, being used as a therapeutic agent against various ailments, protect plants from predators as each plant produce a “sign” mixture of chemical components of essential oils. Approximately 3000 essential oils are derived from about 2000 different medicinal plants and among them, 300 EOs have biomedical properties [12]. Essential oils are extracted from different plant parts such as leaves, fruit, stem, bark, wood, seeds, root, and rhizome. They are stored in canals, secretory cells, and glandular epidermal cells [13]. Essential oils are characterized by their appearance and colour as some are liquid at room temperature while others are resinous or solid. Similarly, variations in colour from blue to dark brownish red and from pale yellow to emerald green characterized EOs varieties [14]. Essential oils are generally recognized as safe (GRAS) so they can be used as a food preservative [15].

Chemical composition of EOs

The chemical composition of essential oils regulates their potential and mechanism of action [16]. EOs are categorized into hydrocarbon and oxygenated groups on the base of their chemical composition [17]. Oxygenated groups contain esters, aldehydes, phenols, alcohol, ketones, and oxidise [18, 19]. while hydrocarbon includes major chemical compound group known as terpenes [20]. Terpenes include isoterpenes, monoterpenes, and sesquiterpenes. Among all of them monoterpenes contributes to 90% of essential oils [21]. Oxygenated monoterpenes and oxygenated sesquiterpenes were identified as main compounds of fresh leaves EOs of *Eucalyptus teretecornis* against *Alternaria alternata* with the minimum inhibitory concentration of 28µg [22, 23]. Linalool and β- Fenchol were reported as the major antimicrobial compounds of fresh leave’s essential oils of *Zanthoxylum armatum*

[24]. The main component of essential oils contributes about 90% while minor components are present as trace elements [18]. Several components are present at relatively higher concentration in essential oils such as 30% carvacol and 27% thymol in *Origanum compactum* oils, 80% d- limonene in peel oils of *citrus limon*, 59% menthol and 19% menthone in *Mentha piperita* and 36% α-phellandrene, 31% limonene in *Anethum graveolens* [25]. Bioactive compound of essential oils are accountable for their antioxidant, anti-carcinogenic, anti-mutagenic, and antiinflammatory activities [26, 27]. Flavonoids, eriodictyol, kaempferol, carnosol, and quercetin constitute of essential oils are responsible for their antimicrobial activities [28]. The quality and quantity of essential oils constituents are effected by numerous factors such as plant species, harvesting time and growing place [29] similarly, temperature, time duration, and solvent used in extraction method also influence their concentration [30]. So that it is necessary to select them according to the claims for which the EOs will be used [31]. Author reported that oxygenated monoterpenes of essential oils extracted from *Cymbopogon citratus* and *Lavandula luisieri* plants showed antifungal potential against dermatophytes. These inhibitory influences on the germination of conidia demonstrate the antifungal activity of this oxygenated monoterpenes. Leaves essential oils of pepper mint are hydrophobic in nature and consist of approximately 300 compounds. Terpenoid are the major group of pepper mint EOs along with minor compounds such as alcohol, aldehyde, lactones and hydrocarbon [32]. Tuyen *et al.* (2021) reported that the leaves EOs of *Zanthoxylum nitidum* composed of limonene, β-caryophyllene, linalool, germacrene D and α-pinene compounds while fruit EOs of *Zanthoxylum nitidum* have n-pentadecane, sabinene and n-heptadecane and stem EOs were composed of 2-undecanone, β-caryophyllene, and germacrene D compounds [33]. Author explained that all these compounds of stem, leaves and fruit possess antimicrobial activity. It has been reported that p- cymene compound had an influence on protein synthesis in the cell of *E. coli* as well as leads the swelling of cytoplasmic membrane to the more extent [34]. Carvacol is phenolic monoterpenoid compounds of essential oils that are closely related to the thymol constitute and have a remarkable antimicrobial potential [35]. Similarly, it has been reported that mixture of carvacol and thymol enhance the permeability of *Staphylococcus aureus* and

Pseudomonas aeruginosa in ethidium bromide [36]. Phenylpropenes is a compound that are synthesized in plant from the precursor of amino acid “phenylalanine”. Eugenol, isoeugenol, cinnamaldehyde and safrole are mostly studied Phenylpropenes. It has been shown that eugenol compound present in the essential oils of

Cinnamomum tamala possess antifungal potential against *Cuvularia lunata* and *Alternaria alternata* and with minimum inhibitory concentration of 8.2µg and 9.5µl respectively [37]. Similarly, another study reported that eugenol leads the cell lysis, deterioration

Figure 1. Extraction methods of different essential oil.

Table 1. Chemical composition and Biological Activity of various essential oils

Essential Oil	Chemical Composition	Biological Activity
Eucalyptus teretecornis	Oxygenated monoterpenes and oxygenated sesquiterpene	Antimicrobial activity against <i>Alternaria alternate</i>
Zanthoxylum armatum	Linalool and β -Fenchol	Antimicrobial activity
Origanum compactum	Carvacol and thymol	Antimicrobial activity
Citrus limon	d-limonene	Antioxidant, anti-carcinogenic, anti-mutagenic, and anti-inflammatory activities
Mentha piperita	Menthol and menthone	Antimicrobial activity
Anethum graveolens	α -phellandrene and limonene	Antioxidant, anti-carcinogenic, anti-mutagenic, and anti-inflammatory activities
Cymbopogon citratus and Lavandula luisieri	Oxygenated monoterpenes	Antifungal activity against dermatophytes
Peppermint	Terpenoids	Antimicrobial activity
Zanthoxylum nitidum	Limonene, β -caryophyllene, linalool, germacrene D and α -pinene	Antimicrobial activity
p -cymene	Monoterpene	Antimicrobial activity
Carvacol	phenolic monoterpene	Antimicrobial activity
Eugenol	Phenolic compound (Allylic-substituted guaiacol)	Antifungal, Antimicrobial activity

of cell walls and prevention of enzymes action in enterobacteraerogenes [38]. The chemical compounds and biological activities of EOs are shown in Table 1.

Essential oils extraction methods

Essential oils are attained from the raw material of plants. The most common methods used for the essential oils extraction are digestion, decoction, percolation, maceration and infusion [39-41].

Academic circles and pharmacy industries generate a remarkable report about the antimicrobial potential of EOs in medical and scientific literature because of their well-recognized usage as a prevalent medicine [42]. Earlier Egyptian medicinal systems involved the usage of essential oils for soothing pain and aches. The practice of essential oils inhibits the growth of spoilage and infectious microorganism that synthetic drugs are sometimes unable to eradicate. Furthermore, essential oils have less side impact on environment than artificial drugs and have more useful properties [43]. Essential oils of *Citrus limon*, *Pinus sylvestris* and *Mentha piperita* are used against throat infections and congestion [44]. Tuyen et al. (2021) showed the antimicrobial potential of leaves, stem, and fruit essential oils of *Zanthoxylum nitidum*. *Nigella sativa* essential oils showed numerous antibacterial, antifungal and antioxidant properties [33,45].

Anti-bacterial potential application of Essential oils

Bacteria are single celled prokaryotic organisms that have cell walls for protection and all the necessary components for their survival and reproduction. Many marine bacterial species are enabling to grow and colonize in the ocean even at low or high concentration of nutrients [46]. Even though bacteria are important indicators of environment [47] but antibiotic-resistant bacteria cause many diseases. These diseases are the outcomes of several dynamic factors such as virulence potential, pathogenicity, and fitness costs of resistance in the human [48]. Due to the resistant of bacteria to antibiotics, essential oils have been proven to be alternative drugs for antibiotic resistant bacteria. As study reported that essential oils from rosemary, cloves,

lemon, thyme, oregano, cinnamon and eucalyptus shows antibacterial potential against *Escherichia coli*, *Trueperella pyogenes*, *Fusobacterium necrophorum* and *Staphylococcus aureus*[49]. Additional study described that essential oils of *Mentha aquatic* L. show the activities against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* strains [50]. Essential oils possess antibacterial potential against numerous bacterial pathogenic strains such as *Listeria monocytogenes*, *L. innocua*, *Salmonella typhimurium* [51]. Pereira et al., (2021) reported the effective applications of basil, anise, coriander, dill, parsley, cardamom, oregano and rosemary essential oils for monitoring the growth and survival of saprophytic and pathogenic microbes. The consequences of their research showed that basil, coriander and oregano EO have inhibitory effect on *S. aureus*, *Yersinia enterocolitica* and *pseudomonas aeruginosa* [52].

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the extraction of essential oils (EOS) from plant material and their Antibacterial mechanism.

Table 2. Example of EOs that mediate the antimicrobial resistant in ESKAPEE pathogens and their mechanism of action

Essential Oil	Bacteria	Mechanism of Action
Rosemary	<i>Escherichia coli</i> , <i>Trueperella pyogenes</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Disrupts permeability of cell wall and cell membrane, targets drugs efflux pump
Thyme, Lemon, Oregano, Eucalyptus, Mentha aquatic L.	<i>Fusobacterium necrophorum</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Escherichia coli</i>	Inhibits quorum sensing, disrupts cell membrane
Satureja hortensis L	, <i>L. innocua</i> , <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	Disrupts cell membrane
Coriander, Rosemary anise, Dill, Cardamom, Parsley, Basil, Oregano	<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Inhibits quorum sensing, disrupts cell membrane
Cinnamon oils	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Proteus vulgaris</i> , <i>Escherichia coli</i> , <i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i> , <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> ,	Disrupts cell membrane, and targets drug efflux pump
Orange, palmarosamoha, palmarosa CN-5	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	Disrupts cell membrane, and targets drug efflux pump
Thymus vulgaris L., Romarinus officinalis L.	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Disrupts cell membrane, and targets drug efflux pump
Thyme, Rosemary, Holy basil	<i>Streptococcus mutants</i>	Disrupts cell membrane, and targets drug efflux pump
Lavandula pedunculata subsp.atlantica (BRAUN-BLANQ.) ROMO	Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> P1418, <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> P637, <i>Escherichia coli</i> P1420, <i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i> BU9399, <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> LA726, <i>Enterobacter cloacae</i> P1374, <i>Enterobacteraerogenes</i> P1260, <i>Salmonella spp.</i> , <i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> PDP533	Disrupts cell membrane, and targets drug efflux pump
Essential oils from the leaves of Tulsi	<i>Escherichia coli</i> , <i>Bacillus anthracis</i> , <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Disrupts cell membrane, and targets drug efflux pump

However, Santra *et al.*, (2020) explained that the growth of bacteria may be repressed by the abundant application of essential oils or their practice at high concentrations and their mode of exploitation leads to decline of the bacterial cells [53]. Similarly, Adamczak *et al.*, (2020) observed the antibacterial potential of 21 plants essential oils against two gram positive bacterial strain *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* and four gram-negative bacterial strains *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Klebsiella pneumonia* [54]. The author found that 19 plant essential oils show activities against one or more bacterial strains. Among all of these oils Cinnamon oils exhibited strong inhibitory effect even at low concentration while eucalyptus, aniseed and camphor

oils exhibited least activity against these bacterial strains.

Furthermore, Sonisangeeta & Soni U.N (2014) reported the antibacterial potential of three essential oils such as orange, palmarosamoha and palmarosa CN-5 against two human pathogenic bacterial strains (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Proteus vulgaris*). Palmarosamoha and palmarosa CN-5 oils have significant inhibitory effect than orange oils against tested bacterial strains. Palmarosamoha oils were more potently inhibit the *Proteus vulgaris* growth. Minimum bactericidal concentrations of these oils were range from 20 to 60µl / ml. However, essential oils of *Thymus vulgaris* L. and *Romarinus officinalis* L. show antibacterial potential against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

strains. 80% strains of bacteria were extremely susceptible to 50 μ l concentration of thymus essential oils. 60% bacterial strains were resistant to 100 μ l concentration of rosemary EO. 1.6 mg/ml was estimated as minimum inhibitory concentration [55]. Similarly, Geetha *et al* (2019) found the anti-bacterial activities of three essential oils such as thyme, rosemary and holy basil by using disc diffusion method against the *streptococcus* mutants that cause the dental caries and found in mouth, intestine and pharynx [56]. The author observed that among these oils, rosemary oils show effective activity against streptococcus mutants at the concentration of 200 μ l. However, Essential oils of *Lavandula pedunculata subsp.atlantica* (BRAUN-BLANQ.) ROMO possess the strong inhibitory activity against nine bacterial strain *Methicillin-resistant*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* P1418, *Staphylococcus aureus* P637, *Escherichia coli* P1420, *Klebsiella oxytoca* BU9399, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* LA726, *Enterobacter cloacae* P1374 *Enterobacter aerogenes* P1260, *Salmonella spp.*, *Acinetobacter baumannii* PDP533. The significant antibacterial potential of *Lavandula atlantica* essential oil (LAEO) is due to the main component camphor (50.4%). LAEO inhibits the tested bacterial strain at the concentration ranges from 3.13 μ l to 25 μ l. The lowest value minimum inhibitory concentration value is obtained on *Klebsiella pneumonia* [57]. Essential oils from the leaves of Tulsi prevent the in-vitro growth of *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus anthracis*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [58]. Additionally, Yu, Z *et al.* (2020) explained the resistance in ESKAPEE pathogens against microorganisms using EOs. Essential oils show antimicrobial activity by targeting pathogenicity, drug resistance, and biofilms. In above figure 3 the essential oils extracted through the hydrodistillation method causes antimicrobial resistance in the family of ESKAPEE pathogens by disrupting permeability of cell wall and cell membrane, targeting drugs efflux pump, targeting microbial communication, targeting R-plasmids and spread resistance [59].

Antiviral application potential of plant derived essential oils

Viruses are acellular, utmost abundant life forms of organisms that particularly infected all living organisms. These are main cause of human suffering and economic defeat [60]. Infection with several viruses such as adenovirus, norovirus, cytomegalovirus and rotavirus can

result in prolonged and severe diarrhoea with graft difficulties [61]. Essential oils were used as antiviral agent without toxicity [62]. The study reported that essential oils from tea tree, thyme and eucalyptus shows antiviral potential against herpes simplex virus [63]. Similarly, bark essential oils of tea tree and cinnamon possess antiviral potential against phage [64]. Leaves essential oils of *Ricinus communis* have antiviral activities against hepatitis A virus [65]. Cimino *et al.*, (2021) described that the EOs derived from *Allium cepa* L, *Allium Sativum* L, *Coriandrum sativum* L, *Cuminum cyminum* L, *Petroselinum sativum* and *Ocimum basilicum* L. shows antiviral activity against HSV1. The 1000 μ g/ml concentration of essential oils of basil, cumin, coriander seeds, garlic, onion and parsley significantly increases antiviral activity. The highest Effective antiviral concentration (EC₅₀) was observed in garlic essential oil which is 320 μ g/ml and its chemical components are di-2- propenyltrisulfide, methyl-2-propenyl trisulphide and di-2- propenyltrisulfide. While lowest EC₅₀ of 2045 μ g/ml was seen in the essential oil of coriander herb and its chemical component is linalool. EC₅₀ represent the concentration of essential oils that protect the 50% of the cells which are infected by virus against cytopathogenicity of virus [66]. However, Chiang *et al.* (2005) stated that linalool shows substantial antiviral potential at the concentration of 16.9 mg/L against adenoviruses. Similarly, the essential oil of *Coriandrum sativum* L. causes 50% lethality in the cells placed in stationary stage of growth at the concentration of 1.6 μ l/ml [67].

Moreover, Akbar *et al.*, (2020) acclaimed that *Ocimum sanctum* Linn. is used for the treatment of arthritis, bronchitis, bronchial asthma, diarrhoea, dysentery, malaria, skin diseases, painful eye diseases, chronic fever and insect bite [68]. The leaf extract of Tulsi were given to the patients suffering from gastric and hepatic disorders [69]. The essential oils obtained from leaves of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn. Have potential applications against virus and fungus [70]. Similarly, the essential oils derived from *Sinapis arvensis* L., *Lallemantia royleana* Benth and *Pulicaria vulgaris* Gaertn and compounds such as monoterpenes of thymol, carvacrol, p-cymene showed inhibitory antiviral effect against herpes simplex virus type 1. The inhibitory concentrations of *Sonchus arvensis* oil, *Lallemantia royleana* oil and *Pulicaria vulgaris* oil for thymol, carvacrol, p-cymene constitutes were determined at 0.002%, 0.037%, >0.1%, 0.035%, 0.018% and 0.001%

respectively. Among all these compounds and essential oils, *P. vulgaris* reduced virus plaque formation [71].

Additionally, Nadjib & B. M. (2020) reported that a range of chemicals and essential oils possess the activities against influenza virus and HSV, adenovirus and mumps virus, dengue virus type 2 and Junin virus, human respiratory syncytial virus, poliovirus, Human Immune-deficiency Virus, Newcastle disease virus, tobacco mosaic virus, yellow fever virus and the viral agent of SARS [72]. The inhibitory influence of EOs has been studied against microorganisms including bacteria, fungi and viruses. Tea tree and Cinnamon bark essential oils showed an inhibition potential against phage. *Cymbopogon citratus* and Roman chamomile oils showed a remarkable inhibition effect against phage. Similarly, the antiviral molecules derived from plants are flavonoids, terpenes, polysaccharides, alkaloids, amino acids, phenols, and essential oils. These are used in phytomedicines and prevent replication of viruses such as hepatitis B, herpes simplex, human immunodeficiency virus and SARS [73]. However, Essential oils from *Juniperus communis* L., *Eucalyptus globules* L, *Cupressus sempervirens* L., *Ocimum*

basilicum L., *M. piperita* L., *Melaleuca alternifolia* *Citrus limon* Risso., *Cymbopogon citratus* (DC.) stapf., *Origanum majorana* L., *Ravensara aromatic* Sonn., *Lavandula latifolia* Medik. and *Romarinus officinalis* has been reported against HSV-1. Essential oils of lemongrass were used for the aliments of infection caused by HSV-1 and also use for the treatment of recurrent ocular and dermal infection. Among all of these oils lemon grass oils showed strong antiviral potential it completely inhibited HIV-1 growth at the concentration of 1% [74].

Similarly, Eucalyptus and peppermint essential oils showed veridical activity against Avian Influenza Virus and Newcastle Disease Virus at the concentration of 2.78% and 13.9% respectively in the absence of skim milk at room temperature for 30 min. The higher concentration of essential oils needs to inactivate NDV while AIV is inactivated by lower concentration of essential oils. Complete veridical potential of essential oils against AIV and NDV in the absence of skim milk occurs at the concentration of 10X and 100X respectively [75].

Figure 3. Antiviral Application of Plants Derived Essential Oils.

Da Silva, *et al.*, (2020) described the antiviral activity of *Citrus reshni* hort. ex Tanaka fruit peel and leaf essential oils against avian influenza virus. Limonene is the major component of fruit peel oils while leaf oils have sabinene followed by linalool [76]. Unripe or ripe fruit peel showed moderate inhibitory effect against H5NI virus at 2.5µl / ml concentration. On the other hand, leaf essential oils exhibited weak inhibitory effect. However, Essential oils from various plants have been used against herpes virus. In the kidney cells of African green monkeys the activities of essential oils of fresh leaves of *Melaleuca ericifolia* Sm., *M. leucadendra* (L.) L., *M. armillaris* (Sol. Ex Gaertn) Sm. and *M. styphelioides* Sm. were examined against Herpes

simplex virus type 1 by the reduction assay of plaque. Essential oils of *Melaleucaericifolia* are 99% more effective against virus than other species [77]. Recently it has been reported that tea tree and *Melaleuca alternifolia* (Maiden & Betche) Cheel. essential oils have been used for the cure of recurrent herpes labialis [78] Correspondingly, [79] previously published the activity of essential oils of *Leptospermum scoparium* J. R. Forst. & G. Forst. against herpes virus. The inhibitory potential of *Leptospermum scoparium* oil against Herpes simplex virus type 1 and Herpes simplex virus type 2 were tested in laboratory. It has been observed that both HSV-1 and HSV-2 are significantly repressed when they were treated with *Leptospermum scoparium* essential oils.

Figure 4. Antifungal activity of plant based essential oil.

Antioxidant application potential of Essential oils

Highly reactive molecules known as free radicals have unpaired electrons and cause numerous oxidative stress [80]. Oxidative stresses include the generation of reactive nitrogen and oxygen species, these species have been associated in aging and numerous uncontrolled practices, as they destroy in cell, protein, lipid and DNA structures [81]. Butylated hydroxyl toluene and butylated hydroxyl anisole are used as an anti-oxidant agent against oxidative damage, however, as their potential toxicity these are studied extensively (Wang *et al.*, 2010). Hence, natural antioxidant agents have gained more attention, as natural constituents may be safer than artificial ones [82]. Essential oils are not only used as nutritional and cosmetic agents, they also

possess numerous activities against microorganisms [83] Bozin *et al.*, 2007) and antioxidant activities [84]. Particularly, phenolic compound of EOs are very effective scavengers of free radicals [85].

Similarly, Wang *et al.* (2017) analysed the antioxidant potential of 26 commercially accessible EOs and their main constituents by determining their total phenolic content, b-carotene bleaching potential, reducing power, free radical scavenging of 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl and antioxidant capacity of trolox equivalent. He reported that EOs of clove bud and thyme borneol showed maximum reducing power and b-carotene bleaching activity at the concentration of 2.5mg/ml among all Eos [86]. Similarly, at the concentration of 1mg/ml both these EOs showed highest value of total phenolic content. On the other hand, clove

bud and ylang-ylang EOs had a maximum trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity while highest 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl free radical scavenger capability showed by bud of clove and jasmine absolute. Author concluded that EOs of bud of clove, absolute of jasmine, ylang-ylang and borneol of thyme have a potential as an antioxidant. However, *Mentha viridis* L. EOs have an oxidative power and are known as a natural antioxidant. Essential oils of *M. viridis* L. showed significant inhibition potential against ABTS, FRAP and DPPH assay by IC_{50} value of $139.59 \pm 3.12 \mu\text{g/mL}$, $101.78 \pm 3.14 \mu\text{g/mL}$, and $80.45 \pm 1.86 \mu\text{g/mL}$ respectively. These antioxidant effects of *Mentha* EOs are because of carvone, 1,8-Cineole, and Terpinen-4-ol components [87].

Conversely, Bouyahya *et al.* (2019) concluded the antioxidant capability of essential oils of *Centaureum erythraea* at vegetative, flowering and post-flowering periods [87]. Carvacrol, methanol and tricosane are the major constituents of CEEOs that are responsible for their oxidative power. He demonstrated that *Centaureum erythraea* EOs showed superior antioxidant potential at the flowering stage against ABTS, FRAP & DPPH by the IC_{50} values of $65.34 \pm 3.71 \mu\text{g/mL}$, $53.25 \pm 2.19 \mu\text{g/mL}$ and $47.18 \pm 3.62 \mu\text{g/mL}$ correspondingly. Moreover, (Helene *et al.*, 2020) reported antioxidant potent of seed EOs of two *Fromomum* Species that is *A. melegueta* and *A. danielli*. EOs of these species has eucalyptol, eugenol, α -terpinol, α -caryophyllene and β -caryophyllene as their main components [88]. *A. melegueta* EOs showed

strong NO^{\cdot} radical scavenging activity while EOs of *A. danielli* showed higher OH^{\cdot} radical scavenging activities. Moreover, both EOs inhibited the lipid peroxidation induced by Fe^{+} and SNP in heart and pancreas of rat respectively.

Additionally, Pavlić *et al.* (2021) reported that EOs of Peppermint leaves showed oxidative power toward the ABTS⁺ radicals assay, cupric ions reducing power and metals chelating assays [89]. The antioxidant potential of peppermint EOs was due to their major terpenoid compounds. They also showed the inhibition potential toward BChE, AChE and tyrosinase. Similarly, Onyedikachi *et al.*, (2022) reported the antioxidant potential of 13 plants EOs against DPPH assay, aldehyde/carboxylic acid assay and malonaldehyde assay. The major compound of EOs that showed antioxidant potent are benzyl acetate in jasmine, limonene in celery seed, α -pinene in juniper berry, citronellol in rose, patchouli alcohol in patchouli and germacrene in ylang-ylang [90].

Essential oils form reactive phenoxy radicals by binding with reactive oxygen species which further bind to ROS and increase the activity of antioxidative enzymes such as CAT, SOD, GSH, and GPx thus inhibiting the oxidative damage as a mechanism of cancer prevention [91]. Legault and colleagues (2003) reported that balsam fir EOs reduce the level of glutathione. Gamma-caryophyllene and α -humulene components of balsam fir EOs mediate the ROS production and decrease the glutathione level respectively in a dose-dependent manner.

Figure 5. Possible antioxidant potential of essential oils against oxidative damage.

Anti-diabetic potential of Essential oils

Diabetic is a prevalent metabolic disease that reduces the life quality of patients. The WHO reported that, in every year 1.5 million deaths occur worldwide and it's believed that diabetic cases are expected to revealed 336 million by 2030 [92]. Several factors such as stress, and unhealthy diet habit. Obesity, inflammation, and low physical potential lead the diabetic problems. Hence, the diabetic problem can be controlled by proper and healthy diet habitation, by taking proper exercise, and by insulin treatment. However, regular injection of insulin leads the discomfort, pain, infection and fat deposition at the injection site [93]. Over a decade, medicinal plants are used as source of medicine against several diseases. A huge number of medicinal plants have anti-diabetic potential and are used to control diabetes. It's indicated that about 72.8% diabetic patients used herbal remedies [94]. *Marrubium vulgare* is a plant that is traditionally used in Algeria for the treatment of diabetes [95].

Yen and his companion in 2015 determine the effect of 29 EOs products against diabetes on T3-L1 adipocytes media. He reported that among 29, three *Melissa officinalis* L. EOs products showed strong inhibition activity against glucose consumption assay and lipid drop accumulation assay due to citral and several other minor components. Similarly, *Syzygium aromaticum* L. and *Cuminum cyminum* L. EOs and their

emulsion possess the anti-diabetic potential against the α -amylase inhibition assay due to 18.7% eugenol and 18.8% α - pinene major components respectively. A5 emulsion of *Syzygium aromaticum* L. and B5 emulsion of *Cuminum cyminum* L. showed significant anti-diabetic activity and inhibit α - amylase with 95.30% & 83.09% correspondingly (Tahir et al., 2016).

Moreover, Diniz et al. (2020) explained the antioxidant, anti-diabetic and neuroprotection potential of six EOs extracted from rosemary, lavender, sage, peppermint, lemon and oregano plants by using HPTLC (a high-performance thin-layer chromatography) technique combined with EDA (effect-directed-analysis) [96]. He reported that oregano EOs have strong antioxidant activity due to the presence of polyphenolic acid while superior α - amylase inhibition showed by rosemary and lemon oils due to monoterpenes constituents. On the other hand, significant AChE inhibition potent showed by rosemary and sage EOs at the concentration of 1 μ l. Antioxidant activity is associated to phenolic components, anti-diabetic activity is related to antioxidant and terpenoid components while AChE inhibition activity is linked to mutual effect of terpenoid and phenols. Hence, the neuroprotection and AChE inhibition activity of rosemary and sage EOs are because of combined influence of terpenoids and phenols [87].

Figure 6. Effects of obesity on insulin resistance and pancreatic beta cell function.

Similarly, Bouyahya *et al.* (2020) reported the anti-diabetic potential of essential oils of *Mentha viridis* L. by using α - amylase and α - glycosidase inhibition assay. *Mentha viridis* L. EOs remarkably inhibit the α - amylase and α - glycosidase by the IC₅₀ values of 101.72 ± 1.86 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 86.93 ± 2.43 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ respectively [87]. These diabetic potential are due to the 1, 8 cineole, carvone and Terpinen-4-ol main constituents of EOs. Bouyahya *et al.* (2020) reported the anti-diabetic potentials of EOs of *Centaureum erythraea* all developing stages such as vegetative, flowering and post flowering. At vegetative phase, *Centaureum erythraea* EOs inhibit the activity of α - amylase and α - glycosidase by the values of 31.91 ± 0.336 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 56.77 ± 1.02 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ respectively [87]. Adefegha *et al.* (2017) explained that essential oils of seeds of *Aframomum melegueta* K. Schum. and *Aframomum danielli* (HOOK.f) K. Schum. showed the anti-diabetic effects [97]. *Aframomum melegueta* EOs have higher α - glycosidase and α - amylase inhibitory potential with the standards of $91.83\mu\text{l/mg}$ and $139\mu\text{l/mg}$ respectively. While *Aframomum danielli* showed strong AChE inhibition.

Mechanism of action of essential oils of Melissa on the expression of glucose consumption activity and adipogenic-specific proteins

Essential oils of Melissa significantly stimulate the AMPK/ ACC pathway in a dose- dependent manner. Activation of adenosine monophosphate-activated protein kinase down- regulates the acetyl-CoA carboxylase by causing the cells to uptake additional glucose from the media as a result inhibition of lipid accumulation in adipocytes occurred. Western blotting analysis was used to evaluate the influence of essential oils of Melissa on the expression of SREBP1, C/EBP and PPAR γ . In evaluation to adipocytes deprived of model treatment, presence of essential oils of Melissa during the differentiation of adipogenic protein resulted in the increase of expression level of SREBP1, and C/EBP but not the PPAR γ . While SREBP1, and C/EBP increase expression levels should enhance the accumulation of lipids into the cells and stimulated Acetyl-CoA carboxylase proteins can prevent the synthesis of lipids [98].

Anticancer application potential of plants derived essential oils

Cancer is reported a major cause of death all over the world, accounting for 9.6 million deaths globally in 2018. Cancer is usually triggered by alterations in proto-oncogenes and main tumor suppressor genes [99]. Stomach, lungs, liver, breast, prostate, cervical, thyroid and colorectal cancer are common in human beings. Among all of them, prostate cancer is more dominant in men while breast cancer is common in women worldwide [83, 86]. The conventional method used for cancer treatments involves chemotherapy, endocrine therapy, and surgical elimination of cancerous parts and radioactive removal of dead tumor cells. Some other additional treatments for cancer therapy involves immunotherapy and hormone therapy but these less significant treatments lead many abnormalities in patient's body as a result normal cells and necessary organ of patients are damage which in turn decrease the life quality of patient [100, 101]. Tumor cells are biologically distinguished from normal body cells in their behaviour such as less permeability of lymph and capillaries drainage system and proliferating blood vessels [102]. Colorectal cancer is the third important reason of death in both males and females in the United States [103]. According to World Health Organization (WHO), cancer of lungs is the second most common non-infectious disease all over the world. It accounts for about 30% and 28% in men and women respectively [104, 105]. About 90% of lung cancer is caused by cigarette smoking, physical inactivity, and usage of tobacco and Westernized foods [106]. Now a day, cancer of breast is the 2nd leading malignancy affecting females throughout the world. In 2018, about 2.08 million fresh cases were diagnosed [9]. (70% of the breast malignance patients have estrogens receptor-positive breast cancer. It is a sort of the cancer in which estrogens are required for growth [107]. The traditional treatment for the tumour is the usage of medicines, chemo and radiotherapies and surgical operations. These traditional management are limited because of the formation of drug resistant malignance cells [108]. Recently, chemoprevention and use of bioactive compounds from plants have been given great deal of attention. Bioactive compounds from the plants have been considered as an anti-cancer agent[109]. Essential oils have been derived from numerous medicinal and ornamental plants. These essential oils have considered as an alternative solution against many infections without any side effects. This alternative solution also emerged to fight against cancer cells [110]. Essential

oils are complex natural organic compounds having multi-constituents system mainly composed of terpenes [111]. The *Morinda citrifolia* L. essential oils possess anthelmintic, analgesic, cytotoxic, hypertensive, anti-microbial, anti-tumor, anti-seditious, immune stimulatory activities [112-114].

Rajiv Gandhi (2020) explained that the cytotoxic influence of *Morinda citrifolia* L. EOs laden chitosan nano-particles against A549 tumor cells line was examined and results in 54% inhibition at 40 μ g/ml¹ concentration [115]. Recently, it is studied that EOs of *Morinda citrifolia* laden chitosan nanoparticles have capability to combat against A549 malignance cells line. However, Rhizoma curcumae is traditional medicine that is widely used for tumor therapy in China are produced by the essential oils of *Curcuma wenyujin*, *Curcuma phaeocaulis* and *Curcuma kwangsiensis* plants. The anti-cancer potential of Rhizome curcumae is due to the terpenoid compounds of essential oils. Their anti-tumor activity leads the cell cycle retardation, apoptosis induction and metastasis inhibition [116]. Similarly, Jeong et al. (2013) reported that EOs of *Pogostemon cablin* (Blanco) Benth. showed the anti-cancer potential [117]. This potential is because of the existence of patchouli alcohol (PA) component that have significant anti-inflammatory, anti-influenza, and

neuroprotective activities. PA constitute possess antitumor potent against colorectal cancer cells of human by inhibiting the growth of tumor cells and promoting apoptosis in human colorectal tumor cells.

El-Abid et al. (2019) reported that fruits and leaves essential oils of *Juniperus oxycedrus* L. have anti-cancer activity on estrogen receptor-positive breast tumor cells [118]. Both oils possess anti-proliferative efficacy however only fruit essential oils retard the growth of tumor cells and induced apoptosis. The anti-tumor efficacy of these oils is due to the presence of PA, PDMS, α -pinene and β -myrcene. Similarly, Xie & T (2022) reported the anti-cancer properties of furanodiene (C₁₅H₂₀O) components that are isolated from the rhizome essential oils of *Curcuma wenyujin* [119]. The inhibitory effect of furanodiene on proliferation of cells were shown in twelve cell lines and cytotoxic influence of furanodiene were shown against Hela, Hep-2, HL-60, and U251 cells at the concentration of 0.6, 1.7, 1.8, 7.0 μ g/ml respectively in a dose-dependent manner. However Yimer et al., 2019 found that *Nigella* spp. possess significant medicinal properties. Among all plants *Nigella sativa* L. is highly important for its medicinal properties and lower toxicity [120]. The *Nigella* EOs and their major components β elemenol and thymo quinone are used against cancer.

Figure 7. Anticancer Applications of Plant derived Essential Oils (EOs).

The para-benzoquinone thymo quinone (TQ, 2) is an active standard that possesses antioxidant, anti-neoplastic and anti-cancer activities [121,122]. Para-benzoquinone is isolated from *Streptomyces* bacteria and thymo quinone is the component of *Nigella sativa* L. and thyme essential oils. It inhibits the growth of tumor cells and induced apoptosis in tumor cells by p53-dependent and p53-independent manners [123]. It's reported that *Curcuma wenyujin* essential oil have effective potential against tumor cell, virus and microbes [124]. Cade oil is used for cancer therapies [125].

Girola *et al* (2015) found that camphene compound isolated from *Piper cernuum* Vell. EOs showed anticancer potential in melanoma cells [126]. The analysis demonstrated that camphene have ability to promote the apoptosis induction through the stimulation of caspase 3 pathway. Camphene also activates the stress signalling of endoplasmic reticulum. Carvacol compound induces apoptosis in the breast cancer cell line (MDA-MB-231) through the permeability of mitochondrial membrane as a result cytochrome C protein release and caspase pathway induction is indicated by the cleavage of poly ADP ribose polymerase and fragmentation of DNA [127]. Citrol compound also showed to promote the activation of caspase and induction of apoptosis in many type of cancer cells including glioblastoma & colorectal cancer [128].

Protein kinase B is a significant molecule that has several roles regards as transcription, cellular metabolism, survival, and progression of cell cycle. Vapours of seed oils of *Litsea cubeba* (LOUR.) Pers. prompted the arrest of cell cycle and apoptosis in small carcinoma lung cells, it is the type of cancer that has high rate of mortality. In this analysis, apoptosis takes place due to the significant reduction in motor protein expression and decrease in the phosphorylating ability of protein pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase 1, leading the protein kinase B (PKB) dephosphorylation and promote the activation of caspase-dependent pathway of apoptosis. Dephosphorylation of PKB deactivate mdm2 and enhances the expression of p21 and initiation of subsequent caspase, resulting G1/S phase of cell cycle arrest. This dual mechanism deal with anti-proliferative plus anti-oxidant activity [129].

Wu *et al.* (2004) reported that organo sulphur component of garlic expressively declines the sustainability of J5 line of liver malignant cells in time or dose dependent methods with compared to control,

via G2/M phase of cell cycle arrest, leads the death of cells by the reduction in the expression of cyclin-dependent kinase 7 and inhibition of subsequent complex of CDK1/cyclin. In tumor cells, expression of nuclear factor- κ B unusually increased and it principally connected with initiation and development of tumor cells [130]. In cancer cells, transcription of nuclear factor- κ B is downregulated by the monoterpene alcohol known as α -terpineol. α -terpineol have significant inhibitory activity against small cell lung carcinoma cell line NCI-H69 [17]. α -terpineol shown synergistic activity along with other monoterpenes compounds known as linalyl acetate against colon tumor cells by inhibiting the expression of nuclear factor- κ B as a result apoptosis occurred [131]. The anti-proliferative action of EOs shown in below mention diagram.

EOs interrupts the potential of mitochondrial membrane triggering a decrease in GSH level and an increase in reactive oxygen species. Cytochrome C protein release, resulting in a cascade of disturbance in the ratio of Bcl / Bax, rise in the activity of caspase 3 & 9, and the cleavage of Poly ADP ribose polymerase (PARP), as a result apoptosis occurs. EOs suppress the action of pPDK1 and mTOR as a result dephosphorylation of protein kinase B (PKB) occurs, which in turn initiates the activity of caspase and turn off the mdm2 activity, resulting an increase in p21, which further promote the caspase activity, resultant apoptosis occurs. Improved p21 level also prompts G1/S phase of cell cycle arrest. EOs triggers a reduction in CDK7 and delay CDK1/cyclin complex as a result G2/M phase of cell cycle is arrested [17].

Application of essential oils in daily life

Tanu and Harpreet in 2016 reported the application of essential oils against pests, mosquitos, and vaginal infections [132]. Due to their lesser toxicity, essential oils have neurotoxic impact against pesticides. They are also used for the ailments of vaginal infection. As shown that sandalwood EOs was used for the treatment of urinary disorders. As the EOs is aromatic substance, therefore, they can provide physical comfort through inhalation and change the behaviour of people. EOs of lavender plant has relaxant and sedative effect Essential oils can be used as insect repellents. Lemon grass EOs along with mint oils has potential against mosquitos due to their main compound citronella.

Syzygium aromaticum essential oils are used as spices in cooking foods as well as for relief of pain.

Essential oils of eucalyptus are used in cold cough, flu, mental clarity, and in aromatherapies. Lavender essential oils attract butterflies, bees, and other pollinators because of their strong odour. It is also used as an insect repellents. Essential oils from *Citrus limon* are used in polish, soaps, fresheners, furniture, and other cleaning products [133].

Essential oils of Zedoary turmeric possess various pharmacological and therapeutic potentials such as antioxidant, tumor suppression, and hepatoprotection. However, essential oils enhance the delivery system of drug transdermal. Essential oils also have ability to penetrate deep into skin and reduce barrier resistance [134].

Figure 8. Possible anti-proliferative activity of essential oils (**EOs:** essential oils; **MITO:** mitochondria; **NFκB:** nuclear factor-κB; **GSH:** Glutathione; **Bcl2:** B-cell lymphoma 2; **Bax:** B-cell lymphoma 2-associated X protein; **pPDK1:** protein pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase 1; **mTOR:** mechanistic target of rapamycin; **mdm2:** murine double minute 2; **CDK:** cyclin-dependant kinase).

Conclusion and future perspectives

Medicinal plants are used as a source of medicine from ancient time. Essential oils are extracted from medicinal plants as secondary metabolites. Essential oils are volatile in nature, diversified in structure, and possess antimicrobial potential. The antimicrobial applications of EOs are due to the presence of bioactive compounds such as alcohol, phenols, alkaloids, terpenoids and other organic constituents. These components are responsible for the bactericidal, fungicidal and veridical activities of essential oils. Essential oils have antioxidant potential, as phenolic compound of EOs are used as free radical scavengers.

Essential oils are widely used for cancer therapies, as the terpenoid compound of EOs retards the cell cycle, induced apoptosis and inhibition of metastasis. Eugenol and α -pinene compounds of *Syzygium aromaticum* essential oils show the anti-diabetic potential. Essential oils directly influence the cell membrane of pathogenic microbes by increasing the permeability of membrane and the intracellular substance leakage as a result respiration of cells and enzymatic system of microbes are disrupted. Furthermore, essential oils also exhibited cytotoxic effects on living cells. Hence, it has been suggested that essential oils might be used against pathogenic microbes as an alternative drug and help in the development of novel medications. The present

review brings detailed knowledge about the biomedical applications of essential oils as antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, antioxidant, anti-diabetic, and anti-cancer agents. Due to the better usage of essential oils, world industries of essential oils rapidly growing and gaining more interest day by day. There is a lack of information about the mechanism of action of individual components of essential oils. Therefore, the future researcher must focus on exploring the mechanism of action of individual essential oils components. It should be important to explore the administration route and development of essential oils as new medicines.

Abbreviations

EOs: Essential oils

LAEO: *Lavandula atlantica* essential oil

ESKAPEE Pathogens: *Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter spp.* and *Escherichia coli*.

HSV: Herpes simplex virus

SARS: Severe acute respiratory syndrome

NDV: Newcastle Disease Virus

AIV: Avian Influenza Virus

CEEOs: *Centaurium erythraea* essential oils

ABTS: (2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid))

FRAP: Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power Assay

DPPH: 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl

BChE: Butyryl cholinesterase

AChE: Acetyl cholinesterase

ROS: Reactive oxygen species

HPTLC: High-performance thin-layer chromatography

EDA: Effect-directed-analysis

AMPK: Adenosine Monophosphate-Activated Protein Kinase

ACC: Acetyl-CoA carboxylase

SREBP1: Sterol regulatory element-binding protein 1

EBPR: Enhance biological phosphorus removal

PPARY: Poly ADP ribose polymerase

WHO: World Health Organization

PA: Patchouli alcohol

CAT: Chloramphenicol acetyltransferase

SOD: Superoxide dismutase

GSH: Glutathione

GPx: Glutathione Peroxidase

Disclosure statement

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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References

1. Mani, M., Sundararaj, A. S., Al-Ghanim, K. A., John, S. P., Elumalai, K., Nicoletti, M., & Govindarajan, M. (2023). Rapid synthesis of copper nanoparticles using *Nepeta cataria* leaves: An eco-friendly management of disease-causing vectors and bacterial pathogens. *Green Processing and Synthesis*, 12(1), 20230022. <https://doi.org/10.1515/gps-2023-0022>
2. Arshad, M. K., Fatima, I., Ahmad, W., Ellahi, S., Mumtaz, M., Akhtar, M. U., ... & Siddique, W. A. (2023). Mint (*Mentha*): A Herb and Used as a Functional Ingredient. *Sch Int J Tradit Complement Med*, 6(3), 38-52. <https://doi.org/10.36348/sijtc.2023.v06i03.003>
3. Yadav, H., Mahalvar, A., Pradhan, M., Yadav, K., Sahu, K. K., & Yadav, R. (2023). Exploring the potential of phytochemicals and nanomaterial: A boon to antimicrobial treatment. *Medicine in Drug Discovery*, 100151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.medidd.2023.100151>
4. Kah, G., Chandran, R., & Abrahamse, H. (2023). Curcumin a natural phenol and its therapeutic role in cancer and photodynamic therapy: a review. *Pharmaceutics*, 15(2), 639. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15020639>
5. Muzaffar, S., Khan, J., Srivastava, R., Gorbatyuk, M. S., & Athar, M. (2023). Mechanistic understanding of the toxic effects of arsenic and warfare arsenicals on human health and environment. *Cell Biology and Toxicology*, 39(1), 85-110. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10565-022-09710-8>
6. Ozma, M. A., Moaddab, S. R., Hosseini, H., Khodadadi, E., Ghotaslou, R., Asgharzadeh, M., ... & Samadi Kafil, H. (2023). A critical review of novel antibiotic resistance prevention approaches with a focus on postbiotics. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2023.2214818>

7. Miguel, S. P., Ribeiro, M. P., Otero, A., & Coutinho, P. (2021). Application of microalgae and microalgal bioactive compounds in skin regeneration. *Algal Research*, 58, 102395. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2021.102395>
8. Álvarez-Martínez, F. J., Barrajon-Catalán, E., Encinar, J. A., Rodríguez-Díaz, J. C., & Micol, V. (2020). Antimicrobial capacity of plant polyphenols against gram-positive bacteria: A comprehensive review. *Current medicinal chemistry*, 27(15), 2576-2606. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0929867325666181008115650>
9. Silva-Igua, L., De La Peña, J., Rubiano, W., & Ruiz-Sternberg, A. M. (2020). Premenopausal breast cancer is a health challenge: nutritional habits show potential to prevent this disease. *Breast Cancer: Basic and Clinical Research*, 14, 1178223420974665. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1178223420974665>
10. Kumar, A., Soni, V., Singh, P., Khan, A. A. P., Nazim, M., Mohapatra, S., ... & Asiri, A. M. (2022). Green aspects of photocatalysts during corona pandemic: a promising role for the deactivation of COVID-19 virus. *RSC advances*, 12(22), 13609-13627. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1RA08981A>
11. Sil, A., Pramanik, K., Samantaray, P., Firoz, M., & Yadav, V. (2020). Essential oils: A boon towards eco-friendly management of phytopathogenic fungi. *J. Entomol. Zool. Stud*, 8, 1884-1891.
12. Yeshi, K., & Wangchuk, P. (2022). Essential oils and their bioactive molecules in healthcare. In *Herbal biomolecules in healthcare applications* (pp. 215-237). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-85852-6.00006-8>
13. Moshrefi Zenoozi, Z., Soltaninezhad, B., Hashemi, M., & Noori, S. M. A. (2022). A review of effective essential oils and their biologically active compounds to protect the safety of food stored against insect pests. *Journal of Essential Oil Research*, 34(2), 111-122. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10412905.2022.2032420>
14. Ruas, A., Graça, A., Marto, J., Gonçalves, L., Oliveira, A., da Silva, A. N., ... & Ribeiro, H. M. (2022). Chemical characterization and bioactivity of commercial essential oils and hydrolates obtained from Portuguese forest logging and thinning. *Molecules*, 27(11), 3572. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27113572>
15. Angane, M., Swift, S., Huang, K., Butts, C. A., & Quek, S. Y. (2022). Essential oils and their major components: an updated review on antimicrobial activities, mechanism of action and their potential application in the food industry. *Foods*, 11(3), 464. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11030464>
16. Pateiro, M., Munekata, P. E., Sant'Ana, A. S., Domínguez, R., Rodríguez-Lázaro, D., & Lorenzo, J. M. (2021). Application of essential oils as antimicrobial agents against spoilage and pathogenic microorganisms in meat products. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 337, 108966. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2020.108966>
17. Blowman, K., Magalhães, M., Lemos, M. F. L., Cabral, C., & Pires, I. M. (2018). Anticancer properties of essential oils and other natural products. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/3149362>
18. Qi, X., Zhong, S., Schwarz, P., Chen, B., & Rao, J. (2023). Mechanisms of antifungal and mycotoxin inhibitory properties of Thymus vulgaris L. essential oil and their major chemical constituents in emulsion-based delivery system. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 197, 116575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2023.116575>
19. Van de Vel, E., Sampers, I., & Raes, K. (2019). A review on influencing factors on the minimum inhibitory concentration of essential oils. *Critical reviews in food science and nutrition*, 59(3), 357-378. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2017.1371112>
20. Dash, D. K., Tyagi, C. K., Sahu, A. K., & Tripathi, V. (2022). Revisiting the medicinal value of terpenes and terpenoids. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.102612>
21. Singh, S. (2023). Natural Product Chemistry in Agriculture. *Green Chemistry in Agriculture and Food Production*, 1.
22. Iseppi, R., Camellini, S., Zurlini, C., Cigognini, I. M., Cannavacciuolo, M., & Messi, P. (2023). Essential Oils and Bacteriocin-Based Active Edible Coating: An Innovative, Natural and Sustainable Approach for the Control of *Listeria monocytogenes* in Seafoods. *Applied Sciences*, 13(4), 2562. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13042562>

23. Guleria, S., Tiku, A. K., Gupta, S., Singh, G., Koul, A., & Razdan, V. K. (2012). Chemical composition, antioxidant activity and inhibitory effects of essential oil of *Eucalyptus teretecornis* grown in north-western Himalaya against *Alternaria alternata*. *Journal of Plant Biochemistry and Biotechnology*, 21, 44-50. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13562-011-0073-2>
24. Ramchandram, R., Ali, M., Mir, S.R., & Sultana, S. (2020). Essential Oil Constituents and Antimicrobial Activity of The Seeds of *Zanthoxylum Armatum* Dc. From Chamoli, Uttarakhand, *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 7(11), 534-541.
25. Santamarta, S., Aldavero, A. C., & Rojo, M. A. (2021). Essential oil of *Cymbopogon martini*, source of geraniol, as a potential antibacterial agent against *Bacillus subtilis*, a pathogen of the bakery industry. *F1000Research*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.54196.2>
26. Ashfaq, M. H., Siddique, A., & Shahid, S. (2021). Antioxidant activity of cinnamon *zeylanicum*: (A review). *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 11(2), 106-116. <http://dx.doi.org/10.52711/2231-5691.2021.00021>
27. Giacometti, J., Kovačević, D. B., Putnik, P., Gabrić, D., Bilušić, T., Krešić, G., ... & Jambrak, A. R. (2018). Extraction of bioactive compounds and essential oils from mediterranean herbs by conventional and green innovative techniques: A review. *Food research international*, 113, 245-262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2018.06.036>
28. Knez Hrnčič, M., Cör, D., Simonovska, J., Knez, Ž., Kavrakovski, Z., & Rafajlovská, V. (2020). Extraction techniques and analytical methods for characterization of active compounds in *Origanum* species. *Molecules*, 25(20), 4735. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25204735>
29. Li, Y., Kong, D., Fu, Y., Sussman, M. R., & Wu, H. (2020). The effect of developmental and environmental factors on secondary metabolites in medicinal plants. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry*, 148, 80-89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plaphy.2020.01.006>
30. Kumar, K., Srivastav, S., & Sharanagat, V. S. (2021). Ultrasound assisted extraction (UAE) of bioactive compounds from fruit and vegetable processing by-products: A review. *Ultrasonics sonochemistry*, 70, 105325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultsonch.2020.105325>
31. Gatti, L., Troiano, F., Vacchini, V., Cappitelli, F., & Balloi, A. (2020). An in vitro evaluation of the biocidal effect of oregano and cloves' volatile compounds against microorganisms colonizing an oil painting—A pioneer study. *Applied Sciences*, 11(1), 78. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11010078>
32. Yingngam, B. (2022). Chemistry of Essential Oils. In *Flavors and Fragrances in Food Processing: Preparation and Characterization Methods* (pp. 189-223). American Chemical Society. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bk-2022-1433.ch003>
33. Son, N.T., Le, T.A., Thuy, D.T., Nguyen, D. L., Tuyen, T.T., Hoang Thi, M. D., & Nguyen, M. H. (2021). Essential oils of the leaf and stem of *Polyalthia viridis* Craib and their biological activities. *Natural Product Communications*, 16(9), 1934578X211032011. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1934578X211032011>
34. Meng, B., Abdullahi, A., Ferreira, I. A., Goonawardane, N., Saito, A., Kimura, I., ... & Gupta, R. K. (2022). Altered TMPRSS2 usage by SARS-CoV-2 Omicron impacts infectivity and fusogenicity. *Nature*, 603(7902), 706-714.
35. Seidel, D. S. (2020). *Phytochemical Effects on Ruminant Gastrointestinal Microorganism Growth and Fermentation* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Georgia).
36. Lambert, R. J. W., Skandamis, P. N., Coote, P. J., & Nychas, G. J. (2001). A study of the minimum inhibitory concentration and mode of action of oregano essential oil, thymol and carvacrol. *Journal of applied microbiology*, 91(3), 453-462. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2672.2001.01428.x>
37. Jafri, H., Ansari, F. A., & Ahmad, I. (2019). Prospects of essential oils in controlling pathogenic biofilm. In *New look to phytomedicine* (pp. 203-236). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-814619-4.00009-4>
38. Thursz, M. R., Richardson, P., Allison, M., Austin, A., Bowers, M., Day, C. P., ... & Forrest, E. H. (2015). Prednisolone or pentoxifylline for alcoholic hepatitis. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 372(17), 1619-1628. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1412278>
39. Chemat, F., Vian, M. A., Fabiano-Tixier, A. S., Nutrizio, M., Jambrak, A. R., Munekata, P. E., ... &

- Cravotto, G. (2020). A review of sustainable and intensified techniques for extraction of food and natural products. *Green Chemistry*, 22(8), 2325-2353. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9GC03878G>
40. El Asbahani, A., Miladi, K., Badri, W., Sala, M., Addi, E. A., Casabianca, H., ... & Elaissari, A. (2015). Essential oils: From extraction to encapsulation. *International journal of pharmaceuticals*, 483(1-2), 220-243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2014.12.069>
41. Granato, D., Putnik, P., Kovačević, D. B., Santos, J. S., Calado, V., Rocha, R. S., ... & Pomerantsev, A. (2018). Trends in chemometrics: Food authentication, microbiology, and effects of processing. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 17(3), 663-677. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12341>
42. Allegra, A., Innao, V., Allegra, A. G., Ettari, R., Pugliese, M., Pulvirenti, N., & Musolino, C. (2019). Role of the microbiota in hematologic malignancies. *Neth. J. Med*, 77(2), 67-80.
43. Žuntar, I., Petric, Z., Bursać Kovačević, D., & Putnik, P. (2020). Safety of probiotics: functional fruit beverages and nutraceuticals. *Foods*, 9(7), 947. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9070947>
44. Leigh-de Rapper, S., & van Vuuren, S. F. (2020). Odoriferous therapy: A review identifying essential oils against pathogens of the respiratory tract. *Chemistry & Biodiversity*, 17(6), e2000062. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cbdv.202000062>
45. Hassanien, A. S., & Akl, A. A. (2015). Influence of composition on optical and dispersion parameters of thermally evaporated non-crystalline Cd50S50-xSex thin films. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 648, 280-290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2015.06.231>
46. Flemming, H. C., & Wuertz, S. (2019). Bacteria and archaea on Earth and their abundance in biofilms. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 17(4), 247-260.
47. Schmidt, J. E., Kent, A. D., Brisson, V. L., & Gaudin, A. (2019). Agricultural management and plant selection interactively affect rhizosphere microbial community structure and nitrogen cycling. *Microbiome*, 7(1), 1-18.
48. Rapanta, C., Botturi, L., Goodyear, P., Guàrdia, L., & Koole, M. (2021). Balancing technology, pedagogy and the new normal: Post-pandemic challenges for higher education. *Postdigital Science and Education*, 3(3), 715-742.
49. Paiano, R. B. (2021). *Endometritis in dairy cows reared in tropical conditions: microorganisms, risk factors, reproductive performance and natural alternative therapy* (Doctoral dissertation, Universidade de São Paulo). <https://doi.org/10.11606/T.10.2021.tde-07032022-114005>
50. Bazzaz, B. S. F., Fakori, M., Khameneh, B., & Hosseinzadeh, H. (2019). Effects of omeprazole and caffeine alone and in combination with gentamicin and ciprofloxacin against antibiotic resistant staphylococcus aureus and escherichia coli strains. *Journal of Pharmacopuncture*, 22(1), 49. <https://doi.org/10.3831%2FKPI.2019.22.006>
51. Abou Baker, D. H., Al-Moghazy, M., & ElSayed, A. A. A. (2020). The in vitro cytotoxicity, antioxidant and antibacterial potential of Satureja hortensis L. essential oil cultivated in Egypt. *Bioorganic chemistry*, 95, 103559. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioorg.2019.103559>
52. Pereira, B. D. F. (2021). *Activity of essential oils and hydroalcoholic extracts from 12 plants against food spoilage yeasts: evaluation of their potential as new biopesticides* (Doctoral dissertation)..
53. Santra, H. K., & Banerjee, D. (2020). Natural products as fungicide and their role in crop protection. *Natural bioactive products in sustainable agriculture*, 131-219.
54. Adamczak, A., Ożarowski, M., & Karpiński, T. M. (2020). Curcumin, a natural antimicrobial agent with strain-specific activity. *Pharmaceuticals*, 13(7), 153. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph13070153>
55. Varadi, M., Anyango, S., Deshpande, M., Nair, S., Natassia, C., Yordanova, G., ... & Velankar, S. (2022). AlphaFold Protein Structure Database: massively expanding the structural coverage of protein-sequence space with high-accuracy models. *Nucleic acids research*, 50(D1), D439-D444. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab1061>
56. Li, X. Y., Moesta, A. K., Xiao, C., Nakamura, K., Casey, M., Zhang, H., ... & Smyth, M. J. (2019). Targeting CD39 in cancer reveals an extracellular ATP-and inflammasome-driven tumor immunity. *Cancer discovery*, 9(12), 1754-1773. <https://doi.org/10.1158/2159-8290.CD-19-0541>
57. Sayout, A., Ouarhach, A., Dilagui, I., Soraa, N., & Romane, A. (2020). Antibacterial activity and chemical composition of essential oil from *Lavandula tenuisecta* Coss. ex Ball. an endemic

- species from Morocco. *European Journal of Integrative Medicine*, 33, 101017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eujim.2019.101017>
58. Hashemi, S. M. B., & Jafarpour, D. (2020). Synergistic properties of Eucalyptus caesia and Dracocephalum multicaule Montbr & Auch essential oils: Antimicrobial activity against food borne pathogens and antioxidant activity in pear slices. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*, 44(9), e14651. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfpp.14651>
59. Agwunobi, D. O., Pei, T., Wang, K., Yu, Z., & Liu, J. (2020). Effects of the essential oil from Cymbopogon citratus on mortality and morphology of the tick Haemaphysalis longicornis (Acari: Ixodidae). *Experimental and Applied Acarology*, 81, 37-50.
60. Reddy, E. P., & Mohanalakshmi, T. (2020). Role of Immunity: Current Status of COVID-19-A Review. *British Journal of Medical and Health Research*.
61. Kim, S. I., & Lee, D. W. (2014). Toxicity of basil and orange essential oils and their components against two coleopteran stored products insect pests. *Journal of Asia-Pacific Entomology*, 17(1), 13-17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aspen.2013.09.002>
62. Sharma, R., Rao, R., Kumar, S., Mahant, S., & Khatkar, S. (2019). Therapeutic potential of citronella essential oil: a review. *Current Drug Discovery Technologies*, 16(4), 330-339. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1570163815666180718095041>
63. Tariq, S., Wani, S., Rasool, W., Shafi, K., Bhat, M. A., Prabhakar, A., ... & Rather, M. A. (2019). A comprehensive review of the antibacterial, antifungal and antiviral potential of essential oils and their chemical constituents against drug-resistant microbial pathogens. *Microbial pathogenesis*, 134, 103580. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpath.2019.103580>
64. Sabo, V. A., & Knezevic, P. (2019). Antimicrobial activity of Eucalyptus camaldulensis Dehn. plant extracts and essential oils: A review. *Industrial crops and products*, 132, 413-429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2019.02.051>
65. Abd El-Hack, M. E., El-Saadony, M. T., Saad, A. M., Salem, H. M., Ashry, N. M., Ghanima, M. M. A., ... & El-Tarabily, K. A. (2022). Essential oils and their nanoemulsions as green alternatives to antibiotics in poultry nutrition: a comprehensive review. *Poultry science*, 101(2), 101584. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2021.101584>
66. Cimino, C., Maurel, O. M., Musumeci, T., Bonaccorso, A., Drago, F., Souto, E. M. B., ... & Carbone, C. (2021). Essential oils: Pharmaceutical applications and encapsulation strategies into lipid-based delivery systems. *Pharmaceutics*, 13(3), 327. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics13030327>
67. Bakkali, F., Averbeck, S., Averbeck, D., Zhiri, A., & Idaomar, M. (2005). Cytotoxicity and gene induction by some essential oils in the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *Mutation Research/Genetic Toxicology and Environmental Mutagenesis*, 585(1-2), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mrgentox.2005.03.013>
68. Akbar, S. (2020). Handbook of 200 medicinal plants: a comprehensive review of their traditional medical uses and scientific justifications.
69. Saeed, K., Pasha, I., Jahangir Chughtai, M. F., Ali, Z., Bukhari, H., & Zuhair, M. (2022). Application of essential oils in food industry: challenges and innovation. *Journal of Essential Oil Research*, 34(2), 97-110. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10412905.2022.2029776>
70. Dhama, K., Sharun, K., Gugjoo, M. B., Tiwari, R., Alagawany, M., Iqbal Yatoo, M., ... & Farag, M. R. (2023). A comprehensive review on chemical profile and pharmacological activities of *Ocimum basilicum*. *Food Reviews International*, 39(1), 119-147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/87559129.2021.1900230>
71. Sharifi-Rad, J., Sureda, A., Tenore, G. C., Daglia, M., Sharifi-Rad, M., Valussi, M., ... & Iriti, M. (2017). Biological activities of essential oils: From plant chemoecology to traditional healing systems. *Molecules*, 22(1), 70. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules22010070>
72. Nadjib, B. M. (2020). Effective antiviral activity of essential oils and their characteristic terpenes against coronaviruses: An update. *J. Pharmacol. Clin. Toxicol*, 8(1), 1138.
73. Goyal, A., & Bengio, Y. (2022). Inductive biases for deep learning of higher-level cognition. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A*, 478(2266), 20210068. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.2021.0068>
74. Asif, M., Saleem, M., Saadullah, M., Yaseen, H. S., & Al Zarzour, R. (2020). COVID-19 and therapy

- with essential oils having antiviral, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory properties. *Inflammopharmacology*, 28, 1153-1161. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10787-020-00744-0>
75. Favre, D., Mold, J., Hunt, P. W., Kanwar, B., Loke, P. N., Seu, L., ... & McCune, J. M. (2010). Tryptophan catabolism by indoleamine 2, 3-dioxygenase 1 alters the balance of TH17 to regulatory T cells in HIV disease. *Science translational medicine*, 2(32), 32ra36-32ra36. <https://doi.org/10.1126/scitranslmed.3000632>
76. Da Silva, J. K. R., Figueiredo, P. L. B., Byler, K. G., & Setzer, W. N. (2020). Essential oils as antiviral agents, potential of essential oils to treat SARS-CoV-2 infection: an in-silico investigation. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 21(10), 3426. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21103426>
77. Farag, R. S., Shalaby, A. S., El-Baroty, G. A., Ibrahim, N. A., Ali, M. A., & Hassan, E. M. (2004). Chemical and biological evaluation of the essential oils of different *Melaleuca* species. *Phytotherapy Research: An International Journal Devoted to Pharmacological and Toxicological Evaluation of Natural Product Derivatives*, 18(1), 30-35. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ptr.1348>
78. Wani, A. R., Yadav, K., Khursheed, A., & Rather, M. A. (2021). An updated and comprehensive review of the antiviral potential of essential oils and their chemical constituents with special focus on their mechanism of action against various influenza and coronaviruses. *Microbial Pathogenesis*, 152, 104620. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpath.2020.104620>
79. Mathew, C., Tesfaye, W., Rasmussen, P., Peterson, G. M., Bartholomaeus, A., Sharma, M., & Thomas, J. (2020). Mānuka oil—A review of antimicrobial and other medicinal properties. *Pharmaceuticals*, 13(11), 343. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph13110343>
80. Sadiq, I. Z. (2023). Free radicals and oxidative stress: Signaling mechanisms, redox basis for human diseases, and cell cycle regulation. *Current Molecular Medicine*, 23(1), 13-35. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1566524022666211222161637>
81. Juan, C. A., Pérez de la Lastra, J. M., Plou, F. J., & Pérez-Lebeña, E. (2021). The chemistry of reactive oxygen species (ROS) revisited: outlining their role in biological macromolecules (DNA, lipids and proteins) and induced pathologies. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 22(9), 4642. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22094642>
82. Hoseinifar, S. H., Yousefi, S., Van Doan, H., Ashouri, G., Gioacchini, G., Maradonna, F., & Carnevali, O. (2020). Oxidative stress and antioxidant defense in fish: the implications of probiotic, prebiotic, and synbiotics. *Reviews in Fisheries Science & Aquaculture*, 29(2), 198-217. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23308249.2020.1795616>
83. Liu, X., Zhou, M., Wang, F., Mubarik, S., Wang, Y., Meng, R., ... & Yu, C. (2020). Secular trend of cancer death and incidence in 29 cancer groups in China, 1990–2017: A joinpoint and age–period–cohort analysis. *Cancer management and research*, 6221-6238. <https://doi.org/10.2147/CMAR.S247648>
84. Masyita, A., Sari, R. M., Astuti, A. D., Yasir, B., Rumata, N. R., Emran, T. B., ... & Simal-Gandara, J. (2022). Terpenes and terpenoids as main bioactive compounds of essential oils, their roles in human health and potential application as natural food preservatives. *Food chemistry: X*, 13, 100217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fochx.2022.100217>
85. Michalak, M. (2022). Plant-derived antioxidants: Significance in skin health and the ageing process. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 23(2), 585. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23020585>
86. Wang, B., He, F., Hu, Y., Wang, Q., Wang, D., Sha, Y., & Wu, J. (2022). Cancer incidence and mortality and risk factors in member countries of the. *BMC cancer*, 22(1), 1-15.
87. Bouyahya, A., Lagrouh, F., El Omari, N., Bourais, I., El Jemli, M., Marmouzi, I., ... & Bakri, Y. (2020). Essential oils of *Mentha viridis* rich phenolic compounds show important antioxidant, antidiabetic, dermatoprotective, antidermatophyte and antibacterial properties. *Biocatalysis and Agricultural Biotechnology*, 23, 101471. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcab.2019.101471>
88. Helene, M. G., Paulin, F. D. H., Jackson, S. A., Christine, S., Elisabet, D., Verlaine, W., ... & Leon, T. A. (2020). GC-MS/FID analysis, antibacterial activity and modes of action of essential oils from three *Aframomum* species found in Cameroon against foodborne pathogenic bacteria. *Cameroon Journal of Experimental Biology*, 14(2).

89. Pavlić, B., Teslić, N., Zengin, G., Đurović, S., Rakić, D., Cvetanović, A., ... & Zeković, Z. (2021). Antioxidant and enzyme-inhibitory activity of peppermint extracts and essential oils obtained by conventional and emerging extraction techniques. *Food Chemistry*, 338, 127724. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2020.127724>
90. Onyedikachi, B., Ejiofor, E., Njoku, C., Ejiofor, M., & Kanu, M. (2022). GC-MS Characterization, in vitro Antioxidant and Anti-inflammatory Activities of Essential Oil from the Leaves of *Stachytarpheta jamaicensis*. *Journal of the Mexican Chemical Society*, 66(4), 433-443. <https://doi.org/10.29356/jmcs.v66i4.1822>
91. Zhang, J., Fu, Y., Yang, P., Liu, X., Li, Y., & Gu, Z. (2020). ROS scavenging biopolymers for anti-inflammatory diseases: classification and formulation. *Advanced Materials Interfaces*, 7(16), 2000632. <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.202000632>
92. Ogunsakin, R. E., Olugbara, O. O., Moyo, S., & Israel, C. (2021). Meta-analysis of studies on depression prevalence among diabetes mellitus patients in Africa. *Heliyon*, 7(5). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07085>
93. Kirwan, R., McCullough, D., Butler, T., Perez de Heredia, F., Davies, I. G., & Stewart, C. (2020). Sarcopenia during COVID-19 lockdown restrictions: long-term health effects of short-term muscle loss. *Geroscience*, 42(6), 1547-1578. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11357-020-00272-3>
94. Al-Samydai, A., Al-Mamoori, F., Shehadeh, M., & Hudaib, M. (2018). Anti-diabetic activity of cinnamon: A review. *International Research Journal of Pharmacy and Medical Sciences*, 1(5), 43-45.
95. Boudjelal, A., Henchiri, C., Sari, M., Sarri, D., Hendel, N., Benkhaled, A., & Ruberto, G. (2013). Herbalists and wild medicinal plants in M'Sila (North Algeria): An ethnopharmacology survey. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 148(2), 395-402. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2013.03.082>
96. Diniz do Nascimento, L., Barbosa de Moraes, A. A., Santana da Costa, K., Pereira Galúcio, J. M., Taube, P. S., Leal Costa, C. M., ... & Guerreiro de Faria, L. J. (2020). Bioactive natural compounds and antioxidant activity of essential oils from spice plants: New findings and potential applications. *Biomolecules*, 10(7), 988. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom10070988>
97. Adefegha, S. A., Olasehinde, T. A., & Oboh, G. (2017). Essential oil composition, antioxidant, antidiabetic and antihypertensive properties of two *Aframomum* species. *Journal of Oleo Science*, 66(1), 51-63. <https://doi.org/10.5650/jos.ess16029>
98. Ramírez-Moreno, E., Arias-Rico, J., Jiménez-Sánchez, R. C., Estrada-Luna, D., Jiménez-Osorio, A. S., Zafra-Rojas, Q. Y., ... & Sandoval-Gallegos, E. M. (2022). Role of Bioactive Compounds in Obesity: Metabolic Mechanism Focused on Inflammation. *Foods*, 11(9), 1232. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11091232>
99. Zhao, Y., Bilal, M., Raza, A., Khan, M. I., Mehmood, S., Hayat, U., ... & Iqbal, H. M. (2021). Tyrosine kinase inhibitors and their unique therapeutic potentialities to combat cancer. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 168, 22-37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2020.12.009>
100. Damyanov, A., Hofmann, P., Geringer, B., Schwaiger, N., Pichler, T., & Siebenhofer, M. (2018). Biogenous ethers: production and operation in a diesel engine. *Automotive and Engine Technology*, 3, 69-82. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41104-018-0028-x>
101. Farokhzad, O. C., Karp, J. M., & Langer, R. (2006). Nanoparticle-aptamer bioconjugates for cancer targeting. *Expert opinion on drug delivery*, 3(3), 311-324. <https://doi.org/10.1517/17425247.3.3.311>
102. Luque-González, M. A., Reis, R. L., Kundu, S. C., & Caballero, D. (2020). Human Microcirculation-on-Chip Models in Cancer Research: Key Integration of Lymphatic and Blood Vasculatures. *Advanced Biosystems*, 4(7), 2000045. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adbi.202000045>
103. Siegel, R., DeSantis, C., Virgo, K., Stein, K., Mariotto, A., Smith, T., ... & Ward, E. (2012). Cancer treatment and survivorship statistics, 2012. *CA: a cancer journal for clinicians*, 62(4), 220-241. <https://doi.org/10.3322/caac.21149>
104. Roman, W., Martin, H., & Sauli, E. (2019). Cardiovascular diseases in Tanzania: The burden of modifiable and intermediate risk factors. <https://doi.org/10.21037/jxym.2019.07.03>
105. Saravanakumar, K., Shanmugam, S., Varukattu, N. B., MubarakAli, D., Kathiresan, K., & Wang, M. H. (2019). Biosynthesis and characterization of copper oxide nanoparticles from indigenous fungi and its

- effect of photothermolysis on human lung carcinoma. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology B: Biology*, *190*, 103-109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphotobiol.2018.11.017>
106. Rock, C. L., Thomson, C., Gansler, T., Gapstur, S. M., McCullough, M. L., Patel, A. V., ... & Doyle, C. (2020). American Cancer Society guideline for diet and physical activity for cancer prevention. *CA: a cancer journal for clinicians*, *70*(4), 245-271. <https://doi.org/10.3322/caac.21591>
107. Matsuda, M., Kido, T., Tsuda, T., Okada, K., Shiraishi, Y., Suekuni, H., ... & Mochizuki, T. (2020). Utility of synthetic MRI in predicting the Ki-67 status of oestrogen receptor-positive breast cancer: a feasibility study. *Clinical radiology*, *75*(5), 398-e1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crad.2019.12.021>
108. Debela, D. T., Muzazu, S. G., Heraro, K. D., Ndalama, M. T., Mesele, B. W., Haile, D. C., ... & Manyazewal, T. (2021). New approaches and procedures for cancer treatment: Current perspectives. *SAGE open medicine*, *9*, 20503121211034366. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20503121211034366>
109. Maruca, A., Catalano, R., Bagezza, D., Mesiti, F., Ambrosio, F. A., Romeo, I., ... & Lupia, A. (2019). The Mediterranean Diet as source of bioactive compounds with multi-targeting anti-cancer profile. *European journal of medicinal chemistry*, *181*, 111579. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2019.111579>
110. Lohani, M., Payne, B. R., & Strayer, D. L. (2019). A review of psychophysiological measures to assess cognitive states in real-world driving. *Frontiers in human neuroscience*, *13*, 57. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2019.00057>
111. Modisane, K. (2021). *Comprehensive analysis of Callistemon citrinus and essential oils using 2-D GCxGC-TOF/MS* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Johannesburg (South Africa)). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9050939>
112. Bastida-Castillo, A., Gómez-Carmona, C. D., De la Cruz-Sánchez, E., Reche-Royo, X., Ibáñez, S. J., & Pino Ortega, J. (2019). Accuracy and inter-unit reliability of ultra-wide-band tracking system in indoor exercise. *Applied Sciences*, *9*(5), 939. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9050939>
113. Safari, W. F. (2020). Similarity check result: Antibacterial And Anticancer Activities Of Marine Bacterial Extracts And Detection Of Genes For Bioactive Compounds Synthesis.
114. Campos, C. J., Goblick, G., Lee, R., Wittamore, K., & Lees, D. N. (2017). Determining the zone of impact of norovirus contamination in shellfish production areas through microbiological monitoring and hydrographic analysis. *Water Research*, *124*, 556-565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.08.021>
115. Gandhi, G. R., Vasconcelos, A. B. S., Wu, D. T., Li, H. B., Antony, P. J., Li, H., ... & Gan, R. Y. (2020). Citrus flavonoids as promising phytochemicals targeting diabetes and related complications: A systematic review of in vitro and in vivo studies. *Nutrients*, *12*(10), 2907. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12102907>
116. Kang, S. Y., Hwang, D., Shin, S., Park, J., Kim, M., Rahman, M. H., ... & Kim, B. (2021). Potential of bioactive food components against gastric cancer: insights into molecular mechanism and therapeutic targets. *Cancers*, *13*(18), 4502. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers13184502>
117. Jeong, S. H., Jung, J. Y., Lee, S. H., Jin, H. M., & Jeon, C. O. (2013). Microbial succession and metabolite changes during fermentation of dongchimi, traditional Korean watery kimchi. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, *164*(1), 46-53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2013.03.016>
118. El-Abid, H., Amaral, C., Cunha, S. C., Augusto, T. V., Fernandes, J. O., Correia-da-Silva, G., ... & Moumni, M. (2019). Chemical composition and anti-cancer properties of Juniperus oxycedrus L. essential oils on estrogen receptor-positive breast cancer cells. *Journal of Functional Foods*, *59*, 261-271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jff.2019.05.042>
119. Xie, T. (2022). *Elemene antitumor drugs: Molecular compatibility theory and its applications in new drug development and clinical practice*. Elsevier.
120. Yimer, E. M., Tuem, K. B., Karim, A., Ur-Rehman, N., & Anwar, F. (2019). Nigella sativa L. (black cumin): a promising natural remedy for wide range of illnesses. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/1528635>

121. Badary, O. A., & AM, G. E. D. (2001). Inhibitory effects of thymoquinone against 20-methylcholanthrene-induced fibrosarcoma tumorigenesis. *Cancer detection and prevention*, 25(4), 362-368.
122. Gali-Muhtasib, H., Diab-Assaf, M., Boltze, C., Al-Hmaira, J., Hartig, R., Roessner, A., & Schneider-Stock, R. (2004). Thymoquinone extracted from black seed triggers apoptotic cell death in human colorectal cancer cells via a p53-dependent mechanism. *International journal of oncology*, 25(4), 857-866. <https://doi.org/10.3892/ijo.25.4.857>
123. El-Mahdy, M. A., Zhu, Q., Wang, Q. E., Wani, G., & Wani, A. A. (2005). Thymoquinone induces apoptosis through activation of caspase-8 and mitochondrial events in p53-null myeloblastic leukemia HL-60 cells. *International journal of cancer*, 117(3), 409-417. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijc.21205>
124. Isnaini, N., Khairan, K., Faradhilla, M., Sufriadi, E., Prajaputra, V., Ginting, B., ... & Lufika, R. D. (2022). A Study of Essential Oils from Patchouli (*Pogostemon cablin* Benth.) and Its Potential as an Antivirus Agent to Relieve Symptoms of COVID-19. *Journal of Patchouli and Essential Oil Products*, 1(2), 26-34.
125. Aboufaras, M., Selmaoui, K., & Ouzennou, N. (2023). Efficacies and side effects of medicinal plants used by patients with cancer in Morocco: A retrospective treatment-outcome study. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 301, 115783. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2022.115783>
126. Girola, N., Figueiredo, C. R., Farias, C. F., Azevedo, R. A., Ferreira, A. K., Teixeira, S. F., ... & Lago, J. H. (2015). Camphene isolated from essential oil of *Piper cernuum* (Piperaceae) induces intrinsic apoptosis in melanoma cells and displays antitumor activity in vivo. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 467(4), 928-934. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrc.2015.10.041>
127. Machado, T. Q., da Fonseca, A. C., Duarte, A., Robbs, B. K., & de Sousa, D. P. (2022). A narrative review of the antitumor activity of monoterpenes from essential oils: An update. *BioMed Research International*, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/6317201>
128. Sheikh, B. Y., Sarker, M. M. R., Kamarudin, M. N. A., & Mohan, G. (2017). Antiproliferative and apoptosis inducing effects of citral via p53 and ROS-induced mitochondrial-mediated apoptosis in human colorectal HCT116 and HT29 cell lines. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 96, 834-846. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2017.10.038>
129. Yu, L., Yu, T. T., & Young, K. H. (2019). Cross-talk between Myc and p53 in B-cell lymphomas. *Chronic diseases and translational medicine*, 5(03), 139-154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cdtm.2019.08.001>
130. Xv, F., Chen, J., Duan, L., & Li, S. (2018). Research progress on the anticancer effects of vitamin K2. *Oncology Letters*, 15(6), 8926-8934. <https://doi.org/10.3892/ol.2018.8502>
131. Kim, T., Song, B., Cho, K. S., & Lee, I. S. (2020). Therapeutic potential of volatile terpenes and terpenoids from forests for inflammatory diseases. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 21(6), 2187. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21062187>
132. Tanu, B., & Harpreet, K. (2016). Benefits of essential oil. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 8(6), 143-149.
133. Irshad, M., Subhani, M. A., Ali, S., & Hussain, A. (2020). Biological importance of essential oils. *Essential Oils-Oils of Nature*, 1, 37-40.
134. Baptista-Silva, S., Borges, S., Ramos, O. L., Pintado, M., & Sarmiento, B. (2020). The progress of essential oils as potential therapeutic agents: A review. *Journal of Essential Oil Research*, 32(4), 279-295. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10412905.2020.1746698>

Cite this article: Shahryar Rasheed, Irum Jamil, Usama Rafi, Erum Bano, Madiha Aslam, Farhad Ali, Fawad Ahmad. A Comprehensive Review on Biomedical Application of Plant-derived Essential Oils. *Materials Chemistry and Mechanics*, 2023, 1(1), 1-23. URL: https://www.matchemtech.com/article_180713.html